

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

Research on Folk Tourism Development Based on IPA and Symbiosis Model Analysis

Author's Details:

An Yajie, Nuerguli· Abudu Suli

(Xinjiang Agricultural University, Urumqi, Xinjiang, 830052)

Abstract

Taking Yotgan Old City in Xinjiang Hotan Region as a case study, through collecting destination-related evaluation contents released on Meituan.com, Ctrip.com and Dianping.com and other platforms, and applying the rooting theory and IPA analysis method to investigate and analyze the tourists' symbiotic perception of the tourism development of Yotgan Old City and the integration of folk culture, and constructing symbiotic and IPA models, we put forward the suggestions to promote the symbiosis and integration of the two in the light of the problems of the scenic area's tourism development: promoting synergistic development and optimizing symbiotic environment; perfecting symbiotic interfaces and improving the tourism experience; and transforming symbiotic modes and improving the symbiotic behaviors.

Key words: Symbiosis theory, Rootedness theory, IPA analysis, Tourism development, Folk Culture

1 Introduction

Driven by the strategy of rural revitalization, China's rural tourism has begun to enter an era of rapid development as an important hand, and the development of rural tourism with Chinese characteristics can promote the modernization of agriculture and social progress in rural areas. Rural tourism can promote rural revitalization in many aspects such as economic benefits, environmental governance, cultural literacy and capital utilization, which is conducive to solving the 'three rural' problems to a greater extent^[1]. Nowadays, tourists are more mature psychologically, not only focusing on material amusement in tourism, but also paying more attention to cultural experience and sense of belonging. Characteristic folk tourism attracts tourists and becomes an important trend in the tourism market because of its unique culture and regional style. Characteristic folk tourism meets the demand of tourists for personalized and in-depth experience, which is a sustainable way of tourism, tourists can personally participate in local traditional activities and experiences, strengthen the sense of belonging to the local community and emotional connection, and play a positive role in the preservation and inheritance of local traditional culture and the promotion of rural development.

With the implementation of the Western Development Strategy by the Chinese government and the concomitant increase in investment in the tourism industry in the western region, the tourism industry in Xinjiang has gained significant promotion and development. Cultural embellishment of Xinjiang is an important part of the Party's strategy for governing Xinjiang in the new era, and the issuance of the document "Implementing Opinions on Promoting the Construction of the Core Area of the Silk Road Economic Belt in Xinjiang" will help to excavate, protect and pass on the folk culture of Xinjiang, improve the quality of tourism, and promote the development of the tourism economy. In recent years, Hotan region

closely around the theme of creating "southern Silk Road culture and folk customs tourism destination", continue to strengthen the integration of local tourism resources to tap and enhance, and continue to promote the quality and upgrade of the tourism industry in the region. Taking Yotgan Old City as an example, this study constructs a symbiosis model and IPA model for the integration of tourism development and characteristic folk customs, analyzes the problems of symbiosis and integration at the present stage, and puts forward the path of synergistic development, aiming at realizing the win-win situation of the inheritance of characteristic folk culture and the high-quality development of the tourism industry.

2 Related Research

2.1 Symbiotic Theory

Anton de Bary first introduced the concept of symbiosis in 1879, referring to the close coexistence of different organisms. This concept laid the foundation for subsequent symbiosis research^[2]. The scholar who first introduced the theory of symbiosis in China was Yuan Chunqing, who believed that symbiotic relationship is formed by different symbiotic units in a certain symbiotic environment according to a certain symbiotic pattern^[3]. The three core elements of the theory of symbiosis include: first, the symbiotic unit is the basic unit of activity and energy exchange between two or more different organisms, second, the symbiotic environment is the sum of all the external factors affecting the symbiotic unit, and the symbiotic environment can be categorized into three kinds of positive, neutral, and negative environments. Thirdly, symbiotic mode is the way of interaction between symbiotic units in symbiotic environment, the behavior of symbiotic mode can be divided into four modes: parasitism, biased symbiosis, asymmetric reciprocal symbiosis and symmetric reciprocal symbiosis, and according to the degree of organization, it can be divided into four modes: point symbiosis, intermittent symbiosis, continuous symbiosis and integrated symbiosis. Tourism is a multidisciplinary industry, which has a strong correlation with various industries. Therefore symbiosis theory applied to the research in tourism is an inevitable choice^[4]. In 2020, based on the symbiosis theory, Wei Fuwei started from the four dimensions of tourism homogeneity, external relevance, gray relevance and outward function intensity to conduct a comprehensive analysis and research on the competitiveness of the Beibu Gulf Economic Zone of Guangxi, and put forward the relevant strategies for the development of tourism competitiveness^[5]. In the same year, Tang Xianling's research focuses on the symbiosis mode of rural tourism development, including symbiosis subject, conflict of interest and governance mechanism so as to promote the sustainable development of rural tourism^[6].

2.2 Folk Tourism

The study of folklore tourism has its origins abroad in the nineteenth century, mainly in continental Europe. Compared with domestic research, foreign research began at an early stage. In 1846, the British folklorist William Thomas coined the word "Folklore", which means "folklore". This marked the starting point of folklore tourism research. In 2017, Zhang Fangyan and Liang Hao conducted a study on the development of folklore tourism souvenirs in China's ethnic minority regions, analyzing the current situation and existing problems, based on which they proposed a strategy specifically for the development of folklore tourism souvenirs in ethnic minority regions^[7]. In 2018, Yang Huo conducted an in-depth study and analysis of the dilemma of the development of folklore tourism in China, she pointed out that at present, there are problems such as over-commercialization of development, over-vulgarization and over-homogenization of folklore tourism in China, and put forward the countermeasures for sustainable development^[8]. In 2019, Wang Qi and Cheng Shuwei, by analyzing the value, conditions, and existing problems of the transformation of Northeast Manchu folk culture, put forward the enhancement path of the transformation of Northeast Manchu folk culture tourism^[9].

2.3 Research Review

At present, there has been extensive research on the integrated development of tourism and culture. Some scholars have elaborated the symbiotic conditions, symbiotic units, symbiotic environment and symbiotic mechanism of culture and tourism, and analyzed the internal logic and mechanism of the integrated development of culture and tourism. Some scholars have also analyzed the industrial symbiosis level measurement, space construction, evolution logic and development trend of culture and tourism integration. Few scholars have explored the symbiosis and integration of tourism development and cultural heritage in Xinjiang scenic spots. Folk culture, also known as traditional culture, through the scenic area to promote and inherit its value can promote cultural inheritance and innovation, enhance tourists' interest in traditional culture and identity, and at the same time for the development of the local economy and the protection of cultural heritage can make a positive contribution. When the development of scenic spots and folk culture are integrated and symbiotic, there are still some challenges and problems despite the conditions provided by the scenic spots. Therefore, based on the symbiosis theory, this study provides new perspectives and ideas on the integration and symbiosis between scenic area development and folk culture inheritance in Hotan area, and contributes to the sustainable development of tourism in the southern border region.

3 Research Design

3.1 Overview of The Study Site

There was a capital city of the ancient state of Ü-Tsang called Jötgön, and in order to let more people in Hotan know about the former glory of the ancient state of Ü-Tsang, a city - Jötgön Old City - was built in Bagchi Town, Hotan County, Hotan Region, Xinjiang, which is the first folk culture and tourism project in the Hotan Region. The staggered white houses in traditional Aiyiwang residential style with decorative elements such as colorful paintings on the porch eaves, brick carvings, wood carvings and flower decorations on the window lattices, and the unique charm of traditional folklore and extremely rich historical and cultural heritage have attracted the attention and love of many tourists, and on June 13th, 2023, it was selected as a national 4A-level tourist attraction.

Yotgan Old City demonstrates the charm of the thousand-year old city through a panoramic interpretation of the prosperous scene of ancient Ü-Tepan, and with the help of modern light and shadow technology, combined with historical and cultural relics, it conveys the cultural and historical significance of the Ancient Silk Road to the tourists. In these performances, actors and actresses perform in traditional ethnic minority costumes. The performances are an important way to display ethnic costumes and one of the ways to pass on and promote folk culture. During the performances, tourists can also enjoy the exquisite costumes made by the Edelweiss Silk Weaving and Dyeing Technique, which is one of the national intangible cultural heritages of China, and from the point of view of folklore, intangible cultural heritages are the concrete expressions of folklore.

3.2 Research Methodology

3.2.1 Rooted in Theory

B Glaser & A Strauss proposed a qualitative research method, based on the collection of rich primary materials, coding, categorization and synthesis to gradually build theories to explore the solution of a difficult problem, and to discover the deeper nature of the relationship between the problem^[10]. In this study, open coding, spindle coding, and selective coding were used, and the software Octopus information collector was used to crawl the data as well as the software NVivo 12 to model the evaluation text of the network of Yotkan Old City.

3.2.2 IPA Analysis

IPA analysis, also known as "Importance-Performance Analysis", was created by Martilla and James in

1977^[11]. The results of the four quadrants through IPA analysis can know in which quadrant the attributes of goods or services provided by the scenic spot are located, which helps to understand the strengths and weaknesses of the goods or services; at the same time, it can find out the priority of improving the attributes of the goods or services, and invest the limited resources in the attributes that are valued by the tourists first in order to improve the competitiveness of the scenic spot.

3.3 Data Collection

Tourist network reviews include tourists' opinions, experiences, suggestions, etc., which are of great help to other tourists in choosing and understanding relevant travel information. By browsing the tourists' online reviews, we can obtain real and multi-faceted travel evaluations. By comparing the overview of reviews of Yotte Old Town in current popular review websites, and also considering the comprehensiveness and representativeness of the feedback of review contents, this study finally selected three platforms, namely, Meituan.com, Ctrip.com, and Dianping.com, as the source of sample data collection. The time span of data crawling was from the opening of April 15, 2023 to the closing of data collection on October 6, 2023. During the selection process, short comments with attraction introductions and lack of subject matter were deleted, and 433 descriptive statements were finally obtained.

4 Results and Analysis

4.1 Analysis of the Rooted Theory Approach

4.1.1 Open Coding

Open coding is the first step in coding a text. Similar concepts are distilled and categorized around the theme to be rooted by tagging the text of the content under study sentence by sentence using tags. In this study, following the principles of open coding completeness, detail, and openness, the relevant information was analyzed line by line and clustered together in terms of the sentences in question, 50 initial concepts as well as 17 categories (Table 1).

Table 1 Examples of open code sections

Scope	Representative Initial Comments (Initial Concept)
Differences in purchasing power	Expensive: tickets are too expensive, cheaper is more or less the same, inside consumption but also their own money
	Affordable: although this is a scenic spot, prices are not high at all
Economic characteristics	Many tourists: just a little bit too many people trampling hazard
	Personalized Service: stay at the B&B at night and watch the show for free, tickets are saved and parking is available
	Ticket Sections: free during the day, 138 RMB/person after 7 pm
	Craft Shortage: not a lot of craft store options either
The Old City Environment	Scale of The Old City: the old city is not big, sneaking around will not take long!
	Old City Sanitation:
	Scenery of The Old City: picturesque, the environment is quite good ah
	Architectural Style: the city walls are high, and the colors are light curry and white, giving people a fresh and natural feel
Location and Transportation	Weather Factor: unfortunately we came in a sandstorm and it looked oozy!
	Surroundings: next to residential neighborhoods and old villages, there are often fairs next to the neighborhoods
	Location: This place is located on the outskirts of Hotan city, a ten-minute drive from the city
	External Transportation: cabs can't be found, serious traffic jams by car

	<p>Dining Experience: from the tea break to the restaurant, taste environment are online, large and small tables are available, suitable for a variety of needs</p> <p>B&B Experience: the owner is very nice, the environment is OK, affordable, stayed 2 days in a row</p>
Service Facilities	<p>Infrastructure: poor guidance before entering the city, no signage, circling the city to find the entrance, no lights at night, no visibility at all</p> <p>Reception services: Yotgan Old City complaints phone has been unanswered</p> <p>Mobility Fatigue: I personally do not recommend bringing very small children and mobility-impaired elderly to watch, because the whole show is really quite tired!</p>
Visit Disturbances	<p>Crowded and Chaotic: every show changes places, people are crowded everywhere, running around, swarming</p> <p>Tourist Quality: national quality is a mess</p> <p>Service Attitude: the actors and staff inside are very enthusiastic</p>
Personnel Services	<p>Communication Barriers: Scenic area attendants do not have, security guards can not speak Mandarin</p> <p>Operational Level: Asked a staff member half a day and couldn't make it clear</p>
Evaluation Outlook	<p>Positive Review: a different kind of city, so shocking, satisfied with the trip</p> <p>Negative Review: really outrageous, sucks don't come!</p> <p>Future Outlook: show time a little earlier, otherwise it's really hard to stay up</p>
Select Orientation	<p>Popular Choices: the entire trip to the southern border, the most impressive memory is here, really very, very much recommended to everyone, will definitely let you surprise!</p> <p>Interest Orientation: If you are not interested in man-made attractions, don't go!</p>
Synthesize and Compare	<p>Scenic Comparison: the depth of the story is not there, and Pingyao ancient city compared to the slightly inferior</p> <p>Value for Money: a superb visual feast for the money</p>
Subject of Image	<p>Image Charm: beautiful women like clouds ah, to friends from abroad excited, a group photo!</p> <p>Actors' Dedication: It's the first time I've seen an actor so dedicated and committed to performing.</p> <p>Characteristics of The Performance: "Immersive" performance through the streets and alleys of the performance space and the form of performance, breaking the boundaries between the stage and the audience area</p> <p>Show Management: Confusing order of performances, speakers say southeast corner but show is in southwest corner</p>
Performance Arrangements	<p>Smoothness of The Program: the connection between programs is relatively tight and natural</p> <p>Detailed Introduction: you can get a paper program at the ticket office, which is very detailed.</p> <p>Filler Program: the Love of a Lifetime program is very ribald and suspected of coping with the audience</p>
Interpretation and Appreciation	<p>Technological Interpretation: light shows, stunts, musical effects are amazing!</p> <p>Wonderful Interpretation: very shocking, after all, look at the whole of Xinjiang has not been so wonderful show!</p> <p>The Atmosphere was Electric: the evening show was really hilarious, two hours in total, and it felt like an immersive experience!</p>
Cultural Awareness	<p>History and Culture: the whole program is very historical and cultural flavor, each program has a historical origin</p>
Folklore Experience	<p>Folk Culture: Programs that feel like an in-depth understanding of Xinjiang's customs and humanities</p> <p>Folklore Interactive: my favorite part is that they can dance and pull the crowd along with</p>

	them!
	Folk Costumes: you can wear ancient or ethnic costumes, which are very suitable for taking photos in the head of this place
	Ethnic Characteristics: There are Yutian old teahouse in the city where you can rest and drink tea, experience the local specialty tea and Xinjiang dried fruits.
Operational Business	Ancient Ruins: a man-made but worthwhile site, a sublimation of the Jotkan Ruins
	Commercial Atmosphere: there is the levity of those famous commercialized old towns
Channel Channeling	Publicity and Marketing: can the official heart operation of this scenic spot, the official photo is not as good as the tourists shot, the scenic spot introduction is not there, so many performances are not said
	Purchase from: Volkswagen Tickets can be purchased for half price, which is really great!

4.1.2 Spindle Type Coding

The main axis coding is to further condense the main categories by analyzing the logical connections that exist between the categories. In this stage, seven core categories were extracted from the 17 categories: market economy, environmental perception, development management, holistic senses, performance forms, traditional heritage, and business strategies, and were divided into three main categories according to the symbiotic system: symbiotic environment, symbiotic interface, and symbiotic mode (Table 2).

Table 2 Spindle type coding results

Main Category	Subcategory	Area	Essential Properties Implied or Reflected by A Notion	
Symbiotic Environment	Market Economy	Differences in Purchasing Power	Different values and spending power can lead to different perceptions and feelings about price.	
		Economic Characteristics	Measures introduced by the Old City to meet the needs of diversified tourists and provide personalized tourism experience	
	Environmental Awareness	Forbidden City Environment	Visitors' perception of the natural and man-made environmental conditions and sanitary conditions in the Old City	
		Location and Transportation Service Facilities	Location and surroundings of the Old City and accessibility to transportation Visitors' experience of the facilities in the Old City	
	Development Management	Disturbed by A Visit	Personnel Services	Problems encountered by tourists during their visit to the Old City Visitors' evaluation of the service process of the staff in the Old City
			Evaluation Outlook	Feedback and suggestions from visitors to the Old City
Symbiotic Interface	Sensory Perception	Select Orientation	Purpose of tourists traveling to the Old City	
		Synthesize and Compare	Visitors' perception of the Old City in comparison to other scenic spots or other things	
	Forms of Performance	Subject of Image Performance Arrangements	What visitors say about the performers in the Old City Visitors' perception of the program design of the Old City	
		Interpretation and Appreciation	Visitors' perception of the atmosphere of the program in the Old City	
Symbiotic Model	A Legacy of Tradition	Cultural Awareness	Visitors' experience of the folk culture and history contained in the Old City	

	Folklore Experience	Visitors' experience of folkloric activities and objects during the process
	Operational Business	Visitors' comments on the authenticity of the Old City
Business Strategy	Channel Channeling	Ways and means of publicizing the old city to the outside world

4.1.3 Selective Coding

Selective coding, also known as core coding, summarizes the existing categories, arrives at the core category - symbiotic development, and constructs a symbiotic model of the intermingling of tourism development and folklore (Figure 1)^[12]. In this study, Yotgan Old City and Folk Customs are the two major symbiotic units, which are the basic units in the symbiosis model; the symbiotic environment is the background conditions and influencing factors in which the symbiotic units are located in the symbiotic relationship; the symbiotic interface provides a place for exchanges and interactions between the symbiotic units; by analyzing the perceptions of the tourists, the present study determines that the symbiotic units are unequal to each other, but the cooperative relationship between each other is still based on reciprocity and interdependence. In the symbiosis model, the pattern formed between the two is an asymmetric reciprocal symbiosis behavior pattern.

The symbiotic environment is an ever-changing process, and through the analysis of the network text of the ancient city of Jotgjan, it is found that the symbiotic environment in which its tourism development and intangible cultural heritage are situated includes the market economy and the perception of the environment. There are two different voices for the purchase of goods: "the people are simple, the price is not high, and the entrance fee is reasonable" and "the price is too high", which indicates that the price needs to be regulated and coordinated by the industries, communities and the government.

The symbiotic interface is the contact point or area where two or more species interact with each other. At this interface, material exchange, information transfer and resource sharing take place between different species, thus realizing a symbiotic relationship. There are a lot of online comments about the symbiotic interface, such as "the actors are dressed in ethnic costumes, dubbed in Mandarin, and their movements and gestures are on point" and "the lodgings are especially unique", and the Yotgayan Old City also integrates local folklore into the design of the infrastructure for tourists to visit and use.

A symbiotic unit refers to the way in which different elements or units exist in an ecosystem that are interdependent, mutually reinforcing, and cooperative. Tourism development and folklore are interconnected in the sense that they can promote and interact with each other. Folk customs represent the local traditional culture, customs and historical traditions, tourism development can provide a better platform for folk customs to attract more tourists to understand and experience the local traditional culture and customs. Folk customs and traditions inject characteristics and unique cultural charms into tourism development, promote the sales and development of traditional handicrafts and specialty products, make the scenic spots more attractive, and promote the prosperity of the local economy.

Symbiosis mode refers to a way of survival in which different populations or individuals are interdependent, interrelated and benefit from each other. Folk customs can be directly felt by tourists in the scenic area, but some of the folk items are commercialized and incomplete, and tourists will not spend money to experience them, so that the inheritance and display of folk customs are limited. This may lead to the local people's less participation and investment in traditional culture, which affects the inheritance of traditional skills, the scale and quality of celebrations, and even makes the relevant practitioners unable to obtain a reasonable income, therefore, the symbiotic behavior mode of tourism development and folklore in Yotgön Former City is an asymmetric reciprocal symbiosis.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the symbiosis model of tourism development and folklore integration

4.2 IPA Analytical Method Analysis

IPA analysis is the main method used for the evaluation of importance and expressiveness, and a two-dimensional four-quadrant diagram is constructed with importance and expressiveness as the horizontal and vertical axes, respectively, and the median value as the split point of the horizontal and vertical axes. The quadrant diagram can visually indicate the situation of various types of elements, which helps to summarize and analyze the problem. Using IPA analysis, the 17 categories obtained from the analysis of the rooted theory are selected as evaluation factors, and the expressive index and importance index of each factor are calculated separately in combination with the network text. The expressiveness index is satisfaction. Three evaluators scored the category perception text separately, with 1-5 as the judgment score, and the three combined to determine the final score. The importance index is the frequency of the corresponding initial concept appearing in the whole text, i.e., the ratio of the number of words in which the factor appears to the total number of words. The measured importance and satisfaction of each factor are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Importance and performance scores for each category

Serial Number	Area	In/%	Pn
1	Area	9.22%	3.35
2	Differences in Purchasing Power	4.61%	2.30
3	Economic Characteristics	2.08%	3.11
4	Forbidden City Environment	4.15%	3.17
5	Location and Transportation	10.37%	2.96
6	Service Facilities	2.76%	2.33
7	Disturbed by A Visit	6.68%	1.03
8	Personnel Services	3.69%	3.81
9	Evaluation Outlook	11.52%	3.68
10	Select Orientation	4.61%	3.65

11	Synthesize and Compare	4.61%	4.55
12	Subject of Image	7.14%	2.52
13	Performance Arrangements	11.98%	4.13
14	Interpretation and Appreciation	5.99%	3.27
15	Cultural Awareness	5.99%	3.92
16	Folklore Experience	2.30%	2.90
17	Operational Business	2.30%	2.40
Average Value		5.88%	3.12

In this study, In/% was used as the X-axis and Pn as the Y-axis, and the median of In and Pn (3.12, 5.88) was used as the coordinate division point, respectively, and the IPA quadrant diagram was constructed by SPSS 22.0 software (Fig. 5). As can be seen from Fig. 5, there are 5, 4, 4, and 3 categories falling into the I, II, III, and IV quadrants, respectively. Quadrant I is the dominant area, and the categories distributed in this area are "scenic environment", "evaluation and outlook", "interpretation and appreciation" and "cultural perception". This indicates that the Yotekan Imperial City has made outstanding achievements in environmental protection, planning and development, artistic performances and cultural transmission, and provides visitors with a rich, unique and satisfying tourism experience.

Quadrant II is the maintenance area, and the categories distributed in this area are "Location and transportation", "Comprehensive comparison", "Selection and orientation", and "Evaluation body ". Among them, the importance and satisfaction of "image subject" is relatively high, indicating that the performers increase the popularity and popularity of the scenic spot. However, the relatively low level of satisfaction in "economic characteristics" indicates that there are some problems in economic operation, product pricing or cooperation with local communities in the Yotgan Old City. In order to improve the situation, scenic spot managers can consider lowering prices, introducing more distinctive products, providing more employment opportunities, or promoting cooperation with the local community to improve the economic characteristics of the scenic spot and increase the satisfaction of tourists.

Quadrant III is the opportunity zone, in which the categories of "location and transportation", "purchasing power difference", "personnel service", "operation and business", "channel business", and "channel business" are distributed. "Channel attraction". Among them, "location and transportation" is the highest concern of tourists, but the satisfaction level is relatively low. Through browsing the network evaluation, it is found that the factors affecting the satisfaction level of tourists include remote location, difficult to take a taxi, and bad road conditions around the area, which affect the travel experience of tourists. Through browsing the network evaluation, it is found that most of the factors affecting tourists' satisfaction are due to the unfamiliarity of the scenic area service staff with Putonghua and business.

Quadrant IV is the disadvantaged area, distributed in the area of the categories are "service facilities", "visit disturbances", "interpretation arrangements". Browsing through the online evaluations, it was found that the factors affecting visitors' satisfaction included dirty restroom facilities, unclear traffic directions, overcrowding due to excessive visitor flow, unreasonable and inconvenient tour routes, and unreasonable performance time.

Fig. 2 Results of IPA analysis for each category of Old City

5 Conclusions and Development Strategy

5.1 Promoting synergistic Development and Optimizing the Symbiotic Environment

First, the market can cooperate with folk artists and traditional craftsmen to cultivate a new generation of folk culture inheritors, create and sell cultural derivatives related to scenic folk customs, such as souvenirs, clothing, music and books, etc. In the process of showing tourists the production of traditional handicrafts, the market can provide opportunities for personal participation in the experience, so as to allow tourists to make some traditional handicrafts with their own hands and leave behind unique souvenirs. In order to satisfy tourists' demand for folk culture and promote the inheritance and development of traditional skills and arts. The government can regulate the prices of folklore-related products and services in scenic spots through relevant regulations and policies to ensure that the prices are fair and reasonable, to avoid overpricing and collusion among merchants to raise prices, and to provide institutional safeguards for the construction of the symbiotic development system.

Second, relevant departments can improve the connectivity between neighboring areas and scenic spots. Plan and increase appropriate public transportation routes, increase frequency and operating hours, urge and guide cab enterprises to increase service points and service vehicles around scenic spots, and, at the same time, encourage cab drivers to provide convenient online taxi services to shorten waiting time and improve service quality. To avoid hindering the advancement of the symbiosis of tourism development and folklore heritage, the cooperation and communication between various management parties should be strengthened, and transportation planning and management measures should be jointly formulated and implemented in order to improve the convenience and comfort of transportation around scenic spots.

5.2 Improving the symbiotic interface to enhance the tourism experience

First, the scenic spot can implement a reservation system to limit the number of visitors per day, and control the flow of visitors through reservation to avoid excessive visitors leading to order chaos; at the same time, it can set up a special reservation channel so that tourists with reservations can enjoy the convenience of fast entry. Strengthen the reception capacity, build more reception centers, visitor service centers and temporary guest rooms, provide efficient and comfortable services, make tourists stay in the scenic area more comfortable and satisfied, and lay a complete foundation for tourism development and folk culture inheritance.

Secondly, the tour time is divided into different time periods, and some other folk performances are

also set up during the daytime, and limit the number of tourists in each time period, so as to increase the comfort of tourists' tour and reduce the occurrence of crowded and chaotic situations, and to unify the time and place of performances to avoid tourists' empty waiting and running, and to strengthen the staff's training in Putonghua and their business ability, so as to provide logistical support for the integration of tourism development and folk culture inheritance. Symbiosis work to provide logistical support.

5.3 Shifting Symbiotic Patterns and Improving Symbiotic Behaviors

First, using popular social media platforms such as microblogging, weibo, jittering, etc., open the official account of the scenic spot, regularly publish attractive content, such as photos of scenic beauty, visitor experience sharing, activity previews, etc., interact with fans and reply to comments, and send coupons or gifts to users of high-quality comments by encouraging tourists to evaluate and share, manage and optimize the reputation of the scenic spot, and improve the exposure of the scenic spot in social media. Degree, through the Yotgan Old City so that more people can understand the folk customs of the Hotan region.

Secondly, in the process of scenic area development imitation ruins serious, scenic area to retain and undertake the original style of the site of Yotgan process can be provided in the interval car excursion services, you can go to visit the original site of Yotgan, on the way to provide professional cultural interpretation services, so that tour guides or interpreters for the explanation of the original style, so that tourists have an in-depth understanding of the local culture, history and customs, so that tourists in the special line of the itinerary to gradually appreciate the cultural relics of the Evolution and change, to create a rich folk culture atmosphere, while reducing the tour time and eliminate tour fatigue.

Conclusion

The symbiosis model of tourism development and folklore integration and the tourists' experience model based on it, which this study tries to construct, combines the theory of symbiosis with actual cases, and helps to improve the theoretical research in the field of tourism development and folklore culture preservation, and the sample size of the study should be increased in the process of the future research, so as to collect more experiences from the tourists, so that the tourist attraction of the Yotgande Old Town will continue to increase and the folk culture of Hotan area will be spread in a better way. folk culture of Hotan region.

References

- i. Shu Boyang, Jiang Yuehua. Theoretical reflection and practical path of high-quality development of rural tourism in the new era[J/OL]. Journal of Central China Normal University (Natural Science Edition):1-14[2021-10-31].
- ii. de Bary A. Die erscheinung der symbiose.[M].Starberg, 1879.
- iii. Yuan Chunqing. A study of symbiosis theory and its application to small economies (above)[J]. Reform,1998(02):100-104.
- iv. Zhou Huiling. Research Review on Tourism Symbiosis[J]. Resource Development and Market,2014,30(09):1134-1137.
- v. WEI Fuwei, HUANG Rongjuan, LU Chunlin. Research on tourism competitiveness in Guangxi Beibu Gulf Economic Zone based on symbiosis theory[J]. Journal of Hechi College,2020,40(03):61-71.
- vi. Tang Xianling. Conflict of interest and governance mechanism of rural tourism based on symbiosis theory[J]. Social Scientist,2020,No.282(10):41-47.DOI:10.19863/j.cnki.issn.1002-3240.2020.10.007.
- vii. Zhang Fangyan, Liang Hao. Development Strategy of Folk Tourism Souvenirs in Minority Areas[J]. Guizhou ethnic research,2017,38(12):192-195.
- viii. Yang Hu. Research on the development of folk tourism in China under the new situation[J]. Agricultural Economy,2018(11):48-49.

- ix. Wang Qi, Cheng Shuwei. On the Tourism Transformation of Northeast Manchu Folk Culture[J]. Academic Exchange, 2019(01):112-119.
- x. LIU Zhongyu, ZHAO Xianghao, LONG Wei. Formation mechanism of consumers' purchase intention under net red live banding--an analysis based on rooting theory[J]. China Circulation Economy, 2020, 34(08):48-57. DOI:10.14089/j.cnki.cn11-3664/f.2020.08.005.
- xi. MARTILLA J A, JAMES J C. Importance-performance Analysis [J]. Journal of Marketing, 1977, 41(1) : 77 - 79.
- xii. li xin, wang qingsheng. Research on the Integration and Symbiosis of Tourism Development and Intangible Cultural Heritage Inheritance--Taking Yangliuqing Ancient Town as an Example [J]. City, 2022(04):39-48.